

THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGISTS IN THE STUDY OF ENGLISH

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Annotation: The use of mass media and technology has come out of the traditional method of lecture from the teacher and the use of students in learning and teaching English as a foreign language through the mass media is today one of the easiest and most effective methods in learning foreign languages. This approach will not only simplify the process of obtaining knowledge from students, but also make them an interesting occupation. The use of media materials, audio-formatted texts, dialogues, listening to podcasts, films with a variety of subtitles from visual materials, allows students to compare the topics discussed in the English language with the help of an image that they can compare and learn through real English human pronunciation. In this article, the views on the role and importance of learning and teaching English through mass media materials will be discussed in the case of using modern technology in teaching English as a foreign language.

Keywords: English, media, technology, visual materials, audio materials, News programs, articles, podcasts.

It gives readers a brief overview of what the mass media is going about and what they should be paying attention to - it helps to concentrate attention while watching the mass media. After describing the theory or concept, the demonstration of the mass media allows the teacher to use the scenes as a case study. This approach helps students develop analytical skills in the practical application of what they have learned. For the first time, the term mass media was used to describe gazettes two centuries ago. Today, the media have different meanings. For example, there are media, print, visual and social networks. Although the mass media can have different forms, the purpose of all the mass media is the same-the mass media is a channel of communication. According to scientists, they argue that language learning is relatively easy by watching foreign media in English.

Improve your reading skills in English i.e. (reading skill) do this also we have media sources coming to your aid. In particular, various English-language newspapers and magazines. For example, in a number of foreign printed publications such as The Washington post, The New York Times, The Associated press, the French press, the Financial times, The Guardian, readers through reading, analyzing and editing News and articles, the reading skills also increases in thinking, outlook.

And now the increase in writing skills (writing skill) in this regard, too, we can rely on Accessible Media. It will be necessary to give the children the task of preparing a script for various small stage productions, or for a school newspaper, so that the students themselves

write articles, messages or news in English. Or social networks, that is, electronic media, that is, in internet networks, they can land their own personal blog in English. Through this also increases the writing skills.

Next skill is speaking, which can be used freely from all types of media. For example, it will be necessary not only to focus on films, but also to behave themselves as actors and actresses, as well as to return such roles, having mastered their accent on what they say. Including, students can prepare themselves an Information Program or a show, talk and make a video and also place it on social networks.

The media created by the students will be an alternative or supplement to the traditional research of the bachelor students. By implementing a digital storytelling project, it is possible to encourage readers' personal feedback and communication.

Studies show that people no clear to learn new and new concepts more easily when presented in oral and visual form than other research suggests that visual media becomes more understandable to people than text media and helps them to remember later. In a 2009 Willingham study, he asks a simple question to express his opinion: "Why do students remember everything on television and forget about what we have taught them?" Because visual media helps readers retain insights and ideas," he said. - American researcher Willingham who provides with answers. It also notes the decisive role of technology to create a learning environment that imposes on the capabilities of one-way communication tools such as movies, documentaries, TV shows and music. It is an interactive education, like visualization and content created by learners.

Advantages of using mass media: many mass media (feature films, music videos, visualization, News) have a very high production quality, capable of demonstrating complex ideas in a short time. This helps develop quantitative thinking. The Media offers both cognitive and immersive experiences. This can come up with a discussion, an assessment of one's own values, and a self-assessment if the scenes have a strong emotional context. The use of Media sources helps to connect students with events of cultural significance. As a result, the positive result of the use of mass media and technology is that teachers need to keep their materials and examples updated. With the help of news, theories taught in the classroom can be attributed to real events and politics.

In conclusion, the popular media (Movies, Music, YouTube) is a familiar tool for students, which helps to attract attention and retain the interest of students in the theories and concepts under discussion. Students will be able to see theories and concepts in practice. In a figurative sense, theories and concepts jump out of the screen. Students will be able to improve their analytical skills by analyzing and analyzing the media with the help of the theories and conceptions they are studying. The use of mass media and technology in the lesson allows students to see concepts and new examples when they are watching TV, listening to music, or when they are in the cinema with friends. Therefore, the use of media materials in the teaching of English as a foreign language is one of the most effective methods. In addition, the interest of students-young people and students in language learning increases in this, at the same time the process of language learning can also accelerate and achieve a faster and more thorough result than traditional education.

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